

Axisymmetric ADE scheme for efficient coupled simulation of hydro-mechanical interaction in geotechnical engineering – application to circular footing and deep tunnel in saturated ground

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Received 10 July 2017; received in revised form 14 August 2017; accepted 18 September 2017

Abstract: Explicit solution techniques have been widely used in geotechnical engineering for simulating the coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M) interaction of fluid flow and deformation induced by structures built above and under saturated ground, i.e. circular footing and deep tunnel. However, the technique is only conditionally stable and requires small time steps, portending its inefficiency for simulating large-scale H-M problems. To improve the efficiency, the unconditionally stable alternating direction explicit (ADE) scheme could be used to solve the flow problem. The standard ADE scheme, however, is only moderately accurate and is restricted to uniform grids and plane strain flow conditions. This paper aims to remove these drawbacks by developing a novel high-order ADE scheme capable of solving flow problems in non-uniform grids and under axisymmetric conditions. The new scheme is derived by performing a fourth-order finite difference approximation to the spatial derivatives of the axisymmetric fluid-diffusion equation in a non-uniform grid configuration. The implicit Crank–Nicolson technique is then applied to the resulting approximation, and the subsequent equation is split into two alternating direction sweeps, giving rise to a new axisymmetric ADE scheme. The pore pressure solutions from the new scheme are then sequentially coupled with an existing geomechanical simulator in the computer code fast Lagrangian analysis of continua (FLAC). This coupling procedure is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order axisymmetric ADE scheme or SEA-4-AXI. Application of SEA-4-AXI for solving axisymmetric consolidation of a circular footing and of advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground shows that SEA-4-AXI reduces computer runtime up to 42%–50% that of FLAC's basic scheme without numerical instability. Yet, it produces high numerical accuracy of the H-M solutions with average percentage difference of only 0.5%–1.8%.

Keywords: hydro-mechanical (H-M) interaction; explicit coupling technique; alternating direction explicit; high-order finite difference; non-uniform grid; axisymmetric consolidation; circular footing; deep tunnel in saturated ground

1. Introduction

Biot's theory of poroelasticity (Biot, 1941) has gained new prominence in geotechnical engineering to understand the coupled response of fluid flow and deformation in deformable porous media (i.e. soils and rocks). The most common examples of this coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M) interaction are consolidation and subsidence induced by fluid extraction from underground formations (e.g. oil and gas from hydrocarbon reservoirs and water from aquifers). In these examples, the transient fluid flow affects deformation in the ground and vice versa (Wang, 2000; Gutierrez and Lewis, 2002; Neuzil, 2003). Thus, consideration of this H-M interaction is essential for the safe design of structures built above or in saturated ground such as circular footing and deep tunnel.

Among various techniques to solve the coupled H-M equations, explicit technique is the most attractive to be used (Minkoff et al., 2003; Dean et al., 2006). The technique is not only simple to be implemented, but also requires less time in building the separate mechanical and fluid flow codes for solving the governing coupled Biot's equations that govern the response of the fluid and the porous medium. Unfortunately, explicit techniques come at a price: they are only conditionally stable. The nature of an explicit technique requires that small time step sizes must be used to maintain numerical stability, placing a strong limitation on the technique. Consequently, the efficiency of computer runtime for an explicit-type

coupling approach cannot be fully exploited for large-scale and long-term H-M simulations that may need enormously long computation time. For example, the H-M response of tunneling in low permeability ground may need a consolidation time up to 250 years to reach the steady-state pore pressure distribution (Prassetyo and Gutierrez, 2016a, b).

One of the most widely used explicit finite difference (FD) code for H-M simulation in geotechnical engineering is fast Lagrangian analysis of continua (FLAC) developed by Itasca (2011a). It is also conditionally stable. The time step size used for its flow calculation must be lower than a critical value in order for the pore pressure behavior to remain stable and monotonic (Itasca, 2011b). Unlike the fluid flow effect that takes place over a considerable amount of time, the geomechanical calculation in FLAC is not of particular concern because the response occurs almost instantaneously particularly for static geomechanical problems.

2. Need for an efficient explicit coupling technique

To improve the efficiency of an explicit coupling technique, one proposed method is to use an unconditionally stable fluid flow scheme that can be sequentially coupled with an existing geomechanical simulator such as FLAC. The alternating direction explicit (ADE) is one of such schemes. In an ADE scheme, two explicit FD equations are executed simultaneously in two physical directions: one in a forward sweep and the other in a reverse sweep (see Fig. 1).

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Fig. 1. Illustration of (a) the forward and (b) the reverse sweeps of the standard plane strain ADE scheme.

To get the mathematical sense of how the ADE scheme works, the following diffusion equation is considered:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \quad (1)$$

As presented in Barakat and Clark (1966), to solve Eq. (1), the ADE scheme executes two explicit FD equations in a forward sweep (Eq. (2)) and in a reverse sweep (Eq. (3)):

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = au_{i,j}^n + b(u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + u_{i+1,j}^n) + c(u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + u_{i,j+1}^n) \quad (2)$$

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = av_{i,j}^n + b(v_{i-1,j}^n + v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + c(v_{i,j-1}^n + v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (3)$$

where a , b and c are the constants defined as

$$a = \frac{1 - \Delta t \left(\frac{1}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta y^2} \right)}{1 + \Delta t \left(\frac{1}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta y^2} \right)} = \frac{1 - \lambda}{1 + \lambda}, \quad b = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda}, \quad c = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda} \quad (4)$$

The final solution is the average of the solutions from the two sweeps defined as

$$p_{i,j}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i,j}^{n+1} + v_{i,j}^{n+1}) \quad (5)$$

It can be seen from Eqs. (2) and (3) and from Fig. 1 that to solve a target point (x_i, y_j) at the current time level $(n + 1)$, both sweeping procedures use a combination of the solutions from the previous time level (n) and the current time level $(n + 1)$. The difference, however, is indicated by the

location of the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ with respect to the location of the target point. In the forward sweep (Eq. (2)), the calculation marches upward in an ascending order of x and y in which the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ are located behind the target point (Fig. 1a). On the other hand, in the reverse sweep (Eq. (3)), the calculation marches downward in a descending order of x and y in which the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ are located ahead of the target point (Fig. 1b). In this way, the explicitness of the scheme is preserved while improving the stability of the scheme. This is the merit of an ADE scheme.

Despite its unconditional stability, the standard ADE scheme has three major drawbacks. First, it is only a second-order accurate scheme in time and space. This low-order accuracy will result in low numerical accuracy when a large time step size is used. Second, it is only valid for uniform grid sizes with the same Δx and Δy for the entire grid model. This limitation prevents the standard ADE scheme from solving large-scale flow problems with increasing grid size towards the far-field boundaries. Third, it is only valid for plane strain conditions. This means that it cannot be used for solving flow problems under axisymmetric conditions.

The main objective of this paper is to remedy the drawbacks of the standard ADE scheme so that the new ADE scheme can be coupled with a geomechanical simulator for an efficient simulation of axisymmetric coupled H-M problems in non-uniform grids. This will be achieved by

formulating a novel high-order ADE scheme capable of solving the axisymmetric fluid flow problem in non-uniform grids. Derivation of the new scheme will be done by performing a fourth-order FD approximation of the spatial derivatives of the axisymmetric fluid-diffusion equation in a non-uniform grid configuration. The resulting fluid flow solution is then sequentially coupled with the existing geomechanical simulator in FLAC. Because the time step restriction is now removed, the H-M simulation can now be performed efficiently with less computation time while still maintaining numerical stability and high numerical accuracy. This paper is a major extension of the newly-derived high-order ADE scheme for solving plane strain flow problem in non-uniform grids (Prasetyo and Gutierrez, 2017a, b).

3. Governing equations for a coupled H-M problem

According to Biot's theory of poroelasticity (Biot, 1941), the coupled equations governing the responses of the fluid (pore pressure) and the solid (effective stress) are related to the changes in fluid content (ζ) and volumetric strain (ε_{vol}) of the porous medium. This relation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = M \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} - \alpha \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{vol}}{\partial t} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} + \alpha p \delta_{ij} = 2G \varepsilon_{ij} + \left(K - \frac{2}{3} G \right) \varepsilon_{vol} \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

where p is the pore pressure; M is the Biot modulus; α is the Biot coefficient; σ_{ij} is the total stress tensor; δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta tensor; and K and G are the drained bulk and shear moduli of the porous medium, respectively. The change in fluid content can be related to the change in pore pressure by substituting Darcy's law in Eq. (8) into the mass balance equation in Eq. (9). After neglecting the gravitational term, the resulting relation is given in Eq. (10).

$$\mathbf{q} = -k (\nabla p - \rho_w \mathbf{g}) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = k \nabla^2 p = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (10)$$

where k is the mobility coefficient ($k = k_H / \gamma_w$), k_H is the hydraulic conductivity, γ_w is the unit weight of fluid, ρ_w is the fluid density, and $\mathbf{g}$ is the gravitational acceleration vector.

In this paper, the contribution from the mechanical deformation to the increment of pore pressure is evaluated in the geomechanical calculation. Thus, during the flow calculation, $\delta \varepsilon_{vol} = 0$. By substituting Eq. (10) **Error! Reference source not found.** into Eq. (6), the transient response of the fluid is then governed by the Laplacian of the pore pressure as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = c_v \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

where c_v is the fluid diffusivity defined as $c_v = kM$.

Eq. (11) is the partial differential equation (PDE) of the flow problem for a plane strain condition (i.e. for a coordinate system adopted in Plane A in Fig. 2). For an axisymmetric condition, the PDE in Eq. (11) may be rewritten in the form of Eq. (12), which corresponds to the adopted coordinate system shown in Plane B in Fig. 2:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{c_v} f \quad (12)$$

where $f = \partial p / \partial t$, the variable r is in the radial direction, while z is in the axial direction. The pore pressure p in Eq. (12) is assumed to be independent in the angular θ direction.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the coordinate systems used for plane strain (Plane A) and axisymmetric (Plane B) analyses.

4. Novel high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme

4.1. Development of high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme

To develop the proposed high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme for a non-uniform grid, the non-uniform FD approximations of the axisymmetric diffusion equation in Eq. (12) must be developed first. To do this, consider a general non-uniform FD grid that consists of four quadrilateral elements in the axisymmetric coordinate system in Fig. 3. From Fig. 3, writing the Taylor series expansion for $p_{i+1,j}$ and $p_{i-1,j}$ to the fourth-order gives

$$p_{i+1,j} = p_{i,j} + \Delta r_+ \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r_+^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} \Delta r_+^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta r_+^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) + \dots \quad (13)$$

$$p_{i-1,j} = p_{i,j} - \Delta r_- \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r_-^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) - \frac{1}{6} \Delta r_-^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta r_-^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) + \dots \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3. Non-uniform FD grid for the axisymmetric coordinate system.

Multiplying $p_{i+1,j}$ in Eq. (13) by Δr_- and $p_{i-1,j}$ in Eq. (14) by Δr_+ , and disregarding the remainder terms gives

$$\Delta r_- p_{i+1,j} = \Delta r_- p_{i,j} + \Delta r_- \Delta r_+ \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} \Delta r_- \Delta r_+^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta r_- \Delta r_+^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta r_+ p_{i-1,j} = \Delta r_+ p_{i,j} - \Delta r_+ \Delta r_- \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) - \frac{1}{6} \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \quad (16)$$

To get $\partial p / \partial r$, Eq. (14) is subtracted from Eq. (13), while to get $\partial^2 p / \partial r^2$, Eq. (16) is added to Eq. (15). To get $\partial^2 p / \partial z^2$, the steps to get Eqs. (13)–(16) are repeated for z and the resulting equations are added. These operations give

$$p_{i+1,j} - p_{i-1,j} = (\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-) \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta r_+^2 - \Delta r_-^2) \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} (\Delta r_+^3 + \Delta r_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} (\Delta r_+^4 - \Delta r_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta r_- p_{i+1,j} + \Delta r_+ p_{i-1,j} = (\Delta r_- + \Delta r_+) p_{i,j} + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2) \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} (\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^3 - \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} (\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^4 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta z_- p_{i,j+1} + \Delta z_+ p_{i,j-1} = (\Delta z_- + \Delta z_+) p_{i,j} + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2) \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} (\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^3 - \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} (\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^4 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial z^4} \right) \quad (19)$$

Therefore, solving Eqs. (17), (18) and (19) for $\partial p / \partial r$, $\partial^2 p / \partial r^2$, and $\partial^2 p / \partial z^2$, respectively, gives

$$\left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right|_{i,j} = \delta_r p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{2} (\Delta r_+ - \Delta r_-) \delta_r^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-} \left[\frac{1}{6} (\Delta r_+^3 + \Delta r_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} (\Delta r_+^4 - \Delta r_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \right|_{i,j} = \delta_r^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2} \left[\frac{1}{3} (\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^3 - \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} \right) + \frac{1}{12} (\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^4 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} \right) \right] \quad (21)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} \right|_{i,j} = \delta_z^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2} \left[\frac{1}{3} (\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^3 - \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^3) \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z^3} \right) + \frac{1}{12} (\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^4 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^4) \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial z^4} \right) \right] \quad (22)$$

where δ_r , δ_r^2 and δ_z^2 are the centered difference operators for the first and second derivatives defined as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta_r p_{i,j} &= \frac{p_{i+1,j} - p_{i-1,j}}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-} \\ \delta_r^2 p_{i,j} &= \frac{2 \Delta r_+ p_{i-1,j} - 2 (\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta r_- p_{i+1,j}}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2} \\ \delta_z^2 p_{i,j} &= \frac{2 \Delta z_+ p_{i,j-1} - 2 (\Delta z_+ + \Delta z_-) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta z_- p_{i,j+1}}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

In order to have the desired fourth-order approximations for $\partial p / \partial r$, $\partial^2 p / \partial r^2$, and $\partial^2 p / \partial z^2$, the higher-order partial derivatives $\partial^3 p / \partial r^3$, $\partial^4 p / \partial r^4$, $\partial^3 p / \partial z^3$, and $\partial^4 p / \partial z^4$ in Eqs. (20)–(22) need to be approximated to the second-order accurate ones. To accomplish this, we perform repeated differentiations of Eq. (12) with respect to r and z until the higher-order terms appear. The differentiations give

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} + \frac{3}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} - \frac{3}{r^3} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^2 \partial z^2} \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z \partial r} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z \partial r^2} \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial z^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z^2 \partial r} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial z^2 \partial r^2} \quad (27)$$

The next step is to use the centered difference approximations in Eq. (23) for the lower-order partial derivatives in Eqs. (24)–(27) and substitute those approximations into Eqs. (20)–(22) and the governing equation in Eq. (12). By performing this operation, the desired fourth-order FD approximations of the axisymmetric diffusion equation can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{r_i} \delta_r + \delta_r^2 + \delta_z^2 \right) p_{i,j} - \left(\frac{\Delta r}{2r_i} \delta_r^2 \right) p_{i,j} + \frac{M_i}{12r_i} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} \delta_r^2 - \frac{1}{r_i^2} \delta_r + \delta_r \delta_z^2 \right) p_{i,j} \\ & + \frac{N_i}{12r_i} \left(-\frac{3}{r_i^2} \delta_r^2 + \frac{3}{r_i^3} \delta_r - \frac{1}{r_i} \delta_r \delta_z^2 + \delta_r^2 \delta_z^2 \right) p_{i,j} + \\ & \frac{A_i}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} \delta_r^2 - \frac{1}{r_i^2} \delta_r + \delta_r \delta_z^2 \right) p_{i,j} + \frac{B_i}{12} \left(-\frac{3}{r_i^2} \delta_r^2 + \frac{3}{r_i^3} \delta_r - \frac{1}{r_i} \delta_r \delta_z^2 + \delta_r^2 \delta_z^2 \right) p_{i,j} \\ & + \frac{C_j}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} \delta_z \delta_r + \delta_z \delta_r^2 \right) p_{i,j} + \frac{D_j}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} \delta_z^2 \delta_r + \delta_z^2 \delta_r^2 \right) p_{i,j} \\ & = \frac{1}{c_v} f_{i,j} + \frac{1}{12c_v r_i} \left(M_i \delta_r + N_i \delta_r^2 - \frac{N_i}{r_i} \delta_r \right) f_{i,j} + \\ & \frac{1}{12c_v} \left(A_i \delta_r + B_i \delta_r^2 - \frac{B_i}{r_i} \delta_r \right) f_{i,j} + \frac{1}{12c_v} (C_j \delta_z + D_j \delta_z^2) f_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta_z p_{i,j} &= \frac{p_{i,j+1} - p_{i,j-1}}{\Delta z_+ + \Delta z_-} \\ f_{i,j} &= \frac{p_{i,j}^{n+1} - p_{i,j}^n}{\Delta t}, \Delta r = \Delta r_+ - \Delta r_- \\ M_i &= \frac{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^3 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^3}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-}, N_i = \frac{1}{4} \frac{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^4 - \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^4}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-} \\ A_i &= 4 \frac{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^3 - \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^3}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2}, B_i = \frac{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^4 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^4}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2} \\ C_j &= 4 \frac{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^3 - \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^3}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2}, D_j = \frac{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^4 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^4}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (29)$$

To assemble the fourth-order approximation of the axisymmetric ADE scheme, the well-known Crank–Nicolson implicit time integration scheme (Crank and Nicolson, 1947) is applied to Eq. (28). The principle of the Crank–Nicolson technique is that difference approximations are developed at the midpoint of the time increment n (Chapra and Canale, 2009). To do this, the temporal derivative $\partial p / \partial t$ is approximated at $t^{n+1/2}$ as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \cong \frac{p_{i,j}^{n+1} - p_{i,j}^n}{\Delta t} \quad (30)$$

while the spatial derivatives $\partial^2 p / \partial r^2$ and $\partial^2 p / \partial z^2$ can be approximated at the midpoint by averaging the spatial derivatives at the beginning t^n and at the end t^{n+1} of the time increment as

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \cong \frac{1}{2} \delta_r^2 (p_{i,j}^{n+1} + p_{i,j}^n) \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} \cong \frac{1}{2} \delta_z^2 (p_{i,j}^{n+1} + p_{i,j}^n) \quad (32)$$

Thus, to apply the Crank–Nicolson technique to Eq. (28), the terms f_{ij} and p_{ij} in Eq. (28) are replaced by $(p_{i,j}^{n+1} - p_{i,j}^n) / \Delta t$ and $(p_{i,j}^{n+1} + p_{i,j}^n) / 2$, respectively. The resulting equation is then arranged in such a way that it is correctly split into the forward and reverse sweeps as previously shown in Eqs. (2) and (3) in Section 2.

Finally, having performed the operation, the novel high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme for a non-uniform grid can be written for the forward sweep as

$$\begin{aligned} u_{i,j}^{n+1} &= \alpha_0 u_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_2 u_{i+1,j}^n + \alpha_3 u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_4 u_{i,j+1}^n + \alpha_5 u_{i-1,j-1}^{n+1} + \\ & \alpha_6 u_{i+1,j-1}^n + \alpha_7 u_{i-1,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_8 u_{i+1,j+1}^n + \beta_1 (u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} - u_{i-1,j}^n) + \beta_2 (u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} - u_{i,j-1}^n) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

and for the reverse sweep as

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 v_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 v_{i-1,j}^n + \alpha_2 v_{i+1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_3 v_{i,j-1}^n + \alpha_4 v_{i,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_5 v_{i-1,j-1}^n +$$

$$\alpha_6 v_{i+1,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_7 v_{i-1,j+1}^n + \alpha_8 v_{i+1,j+1}^{n+1} + \beta_3 (v_{i+1,j}^n - v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + \beta_4 (v_{i,j+1}^n - v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (34)$$

where $\alpha_0 - \alpha_8$ and $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ are the grid size-dependent constants. The expressions for these constants are given in Eqs. (A1)–(A5) in the Appendix to prevent encumbering the main presentation in the text. These constants are made up of more terms than those in Eq. (4) to account for non-uniformity in grid size. Fig. 4 illustrates the arrangement of the calculation sweeps for the newly-derived high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme. Compared to the standard scheme in Fig. 1, the new ADE scheme involves more contributing points in the calculation of the target point because of the fourth-order approximation, e.g. additional diagonal points from the cross-derivatives. Nevertheless, the new scheme still maintains the nine-point stencil, preserving its compactness.

The axisymmetric ADE scheme in Eqs. (33) and (34) is valid for all points inside the FD grid except for the points along the axis of symmetry or at $r = 0$ (see Fig. 5). The PDE in Eq. (12) has a singularity at $r = 0$ because the equation encounters a division of $0/0$ for the $(1/r)\partial p/\partial r$ term. To remove this singularity, L'Hospital's rule must be used. The numerator and the denominator of the term $(1/r)\partial p/\partial r$ must be successively differentiated with respect to r until a finite limit is achieved. Eq. (35) shows the operation of L'Hospital's rule for the $(1/r)\partial p/\partial r$ term, in which the term simply becomes $\partial^2 p/\partial r^2$.

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=0} = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right)}{\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r)} \Big|_{r=0} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} \Big|_{r=0} \quad (35)$$

After substituting $\partial^2 p/\partial r^2$ for $(1/r)\partial p/\partial r$ in Eq. (12), the PDE becomes that shown in Eq. (36). This is the governing PDE that needs to be discretized to obtain the high-order ADE scheme for the boundary points located along the axis of symmetry (called the axisymmetric boundary points from now on).

$$2 \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{c_v} f \quad (36)$$

For the axisymmetric boundary points, the steps to develop the corresponding high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme are the same as those for the interior points. The steps will not be repeated here but the final arrangements will be given.

Having performed the operation presented in Eqs. (13)–(34), the novel high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme for the axisymmetric boundary points can be written for the forward sweep as

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 u_{i,j}^n + \alpha_2 u_{i+1,j}^n + \alpha_3 u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_4 u_{i,j+1}^n + \alpha_6 u_{i+1,j-1}^n + \alpha_8 u_{i+1,j+1}^n + \beta_2 (u_{i,j-1}^n - u_{i,j-1}^{n+1}) \quad (37)$$

and for the reverse sweep as

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 v_{i,j}^n + \alpha_2 v_{i+1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_3 v_{i,j-1}^n + \alpha_4 v_{i,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_6 v_{i+1,j-1}^n + \alpha_8 v_{i+1,j+1}^{n+1} + \beta_3 (v_{i+1,j}^n - v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + \beta_4 (v_{i,j+1}^n - v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (38)$$

Note that the constants $\alpha_1, \alpha_5, \alpha_7,$ and β_1 are now equal to zero, meaning that fewer neighboring points are needed in the calculation. The expression for grid size-dependent constants for the axisymmetric boundary points are given in Eq. (A6) in the Appendix.

Note that in the above derivations, the mobility coefficient $k = k_{ht}/\gamma_w$ has been assumed to be constant, causing the fluid diffusivity c_v in the grid size-dependent constants to be constant as well. The permeability of a porous medium can certainly be made anisotropic by having different mobility coefficients in the radial and axial directions (k_r and k_z , respectively). To accommodate this anisotropy, Eqs. (12) and (36) can be rewritten in more general forms as

$$c_v^r \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + c_v^r \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + c_v^z \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} = f \quad (39)$$

$$2c_v^r \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + c_v^z \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} = f \quad (40)$$

Fig. 4. Illustration of (a) the forward and (b) the reverse sweeps of the new high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme.

Fig. 5. Illustration of an axisymmetric consolidation showing location of the axis of symmetry.

where $c_v^r = k_r M$ and $c_v^z = k_z M$. By repeating the steps to derive the high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme, the constants c_v^r and c_v^z will continuously follow the derivative terms that result from taking the partial derivative with respect to r and z , respectively. Consequently, the grid size-dependent constants in Eqs. (A1)–(A6) will consist of c_v^r and c_v^z instead of just c_v , causing the value of each grid size-dependent constant to be unique for each grid point. Therefore, the permeability of a porous medium in a coupled model can be made anisotropic by simply assigning the desired c_v^r and c_v^z values to the corresponding grid points in the model.

4.2. Proof of convergence

Convergence is the attribute that the newly-derived ADE scheme must have to instill confidence in its results. According to the Lax-Richtmyer equivalence theorem, stability and consistency are the conditions to be satisfied by an FD scheme in order for it to be called a convergent scheme (Richtmyer and Morton, 1967). Stability means that errors at any stage of the computation decay as the computation progresses, while consistency means that the FD scheme reduces to the governing PDE as the increments in the independent variables vanish.

4.2.1. Stability

To prove the stability of the new ADE scheme, the von Neumann stability analysis is used. The new ADE scheme can be said to be stable if the amplification factor of the solution meets the criterion $|G(\theta)| \leq 1$ when the solution is advanced one time step, expressing the decay of the frequency amplitude of the solution (Barakat and Clark, 1966; Hoffman, 2001; Strikwerda, 2004; Mazumder, 2016). To use the von Neumann stability analysis, the pore pressure solutions to the forward and reverse sweeps are rewritten in separable Fourier expansions as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_{i\pm 1, j\pm 1}^n &= u_{i, j}^n e^{\pm i\theta_r} e^{\pm i\theta_z}, & u_{i\pm 1, j\pm 1}^{n+1} &= u_{i, j}^{n+1} e^{\pm i\theta_r} e^{\pm i\theta_z} \\ v_{i\pm 1, j\pm 1}^n &= v_{i, j}^n e^{\pm i\theta_r} e^{\pm i\theta_z}, & v_{i\pm 1, j\pm 1}^{n+1} &= v_{i, j}^{n+1} e^{\pm i\theta_r} e^{\pm i\theta_z} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (41)$$

where e is the exponential function; i is the imaginary number $i = \sqrt{-1}$; and θ is the phase angle. To obtain the expressions for calculating $G(\theta)$, Eq. (41) is then substituted into the new ADE schemes in Eqs. (33) and (34) for the interior points, and in Eqs. (37) and (38) for the axisymmetric boundary points.

For the interior points, the substitution yields the expression for calculating $G(\theta)$ for the forward sweep as

$$G(\theta) = u_{i, j}^{n+1} / u_{i, j}^n =$$

$$\frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_2 e^{i\theta_x} + \alpha_4 e^{i\theta_y} + \alpha_6 e^{i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} + \alpha_8 e^{i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y} - \beta_1 e^{-i\theta_x} - \beta_2 e^{-i\theta_y}}{1 - (\alpha_1 + \beta_1) e^{-i\theta_x} - (\alpha_3 + \beta_2) e^{-i\theta_y} - \alpha_5 e^{-i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} - \alpha_7 e^{-i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y}} \quad (42)$$

and for the reverse sweep as

$$G(\theta) = v_{i, j}^{n+1} / v_{i, j}^n = \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 e^{-i\theta_x} + \alpha_3 e^{-i\theta_y} + \alpha_5 e^{-i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} + \alpha_7 e^{-i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y} + \beta_3 e^{i\theta_x} + \beta_4 e^{i\theta_y}}{1 - (\alpha_2 - \beta_3) e^{i\theta_x} - (\alpha_4 - \beta_4) e^{i\theta_y} - \alpha_6 e^{i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} - \alpha_8 e^{i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y}} \quad (43)$$

Likewise, for the axisymmetric boundary points, the substitution yields the expressions for calculating $G(\theta)$ for the forward sweep as

$$G(\theta) = u_{i, j}^{n+1} / u_{i, j}^n = \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_2 e^{i\theta_x} + \alpha_4 e^{i\theta_y} + \alpha_6 e^{i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} + \alpha_8 e^{i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y} - \beta_2 e^{-i\theta_y}}{1 - (\alpha_3 + \beta_2) e^{-i\theta_y}} \quad (44)$$

and for the reverse sweep as

$$G(\theta) = v_{i, j}^{n+1} / v_{i, j}^n = \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_3 e^{-i\theta_y} + \beta_3 e^{i\theta_x} + \beta_4 e^{i\theta_y}}{1 - (\alpha_2 - \beta_3) e^{i\theta_x} - (\alpha_4 - \beta_4) e^{i\theta_y} - \alpha_6 e^{i\theta_x} e^{-i\theta_y} - \alpha_8 e^{i\theta_x} e^{i\theta_y}} \quad (45)$$

To check if the criterion for stability is met for each sweep, i.e. $|G(\theta)| \leq 1$, graphical examination of $G(\theta)$ will be helpful. To do this, the material properties from the axisymmetric consolidation problem in Section 5 are used to calculate the grid size-dependent constants from Eqs. (A1)–(A6). The resulting values of the constants are substituted in Eqs. (42)–(45) and the resulting values of $G(\theta)$ with varying θ are then plotted. Fig. 6 shows the plots of $G(\theta)$ for the forward and reverse sweeps for the interior points (Fig. 6a) and for the axisymmetric boundary points (Fig. 6b). It can be seen that as θ varies, the set of points marked out by $G(\theta)$ lie within the unit circle with the radius of unity, ensuring that the FD solutions are bounded and that the new ADE schemes are unconditionally stable. In either interior or axisymmetric boundary points, the shape of the $G(\theta)$ curve for each sweep is not the same as it should be because the equations for $G(\theta)$ for each sweep are also different, resulting in different values of grid-size dependent constants.

4.2.2. Consistency

The consistency condition requires that the truncation errors of the newly-derived ADE scheme vanish as Δr , Δz , and Δt approach zero. The behavior of the truncation errors for the interior grids can be investigated by looking at Eq. (28) because the discretization of the high-order axisymmetric ADE scheme comes from this equation. Eq. (28) may be rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \tau_{i, j} = 0 \quad (46)$$

where $\tau_{i, j}$ is the truncation error resulting from expanding the governing equation in Eq. (12) to the fourth-order. The truncation error is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{i, j} &= \frac{\Delta r}{2r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} - \frac{M}{12r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} \right) \\ &- \frac{N}{12r} \left(-\frac{3}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{3}{r^3} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^2 \partial z^2} \right) \\ &- \frac{A}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} \right) \\ &- \frac{B}{12} \left(-\frac{3}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{3}{r^3} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial r^2 \partial z^2} \right) \\ &- \frac{C}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r \partial z} + \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial r \partial z^2} \right) + \frac{D}{12} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial z \partial r^2} + \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial z^2 \partial r^2} \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{12c_v r} \left(M \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} + N \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial r^2} - \frac{N}{r} \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{12c_v} \left(A \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} + B \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial r^2} - \frac{B}{r} \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$+\frac{1}{12c_v}\left(C\frac{\partial f}{\partial z}+D\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial z^2}\right) \quad (47)$$

Fig. 6. Variation of $G(\theta)$ for the forward and reverse sweeps of the new axisymmetric ADE scheme for (a) the interior and (b) the axisymmetric boundary points.

Assuming that uniform grid sizes are used, $\Delta r_- = \Delta r_+ = \Delta r$ and $\Delta z_- = \Delta z_+ = \Delta z$, the constants M, N, A, B, C , and D defined in Eq. (29) become $\Delta r^3, 0, 0, \Delta r^2, 0$ and Δz^2 , respectively. Clearly, when these grid sizes approach zero, π_j will be zero and Eq. (46) reduces to the governing PDE defined in Eq. (12), guaranteeing the consistency of the new scheme. A similar approach can be taken for the axisymmetric boundary points in which when the truncation error goes to zero, the governing PDE in Eq. (36) will be recovered.

4.3. Efficient sequential coupling technique

The coupled problems in this paper will be modeled and solved in FLAC. At every time step, the newly-derived axisymmetric ADE scheme will first be executed to solve the fluid flow problem, and then the system will be sequentially brought to geomechanical equilibrium using FLAC's built-in geomechanical simulator. From now on, the use of the axisymmetric ADE schemes in FLAC is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order axisymmetric ADE schemes or SEA-4-AXI. This coupling technique is written in FLAC's programming language called FISH

(Itasca, 2011c). Fig. 7 shows the flow chart of SEA-4-AXI to solve the coupled problems in this paper.

Fig. 7. The sequential coupling technique in FLAC using the fourth-order axisymmetric ADE schemes (SEA-4-AXI).

From the state of geomechanical equilibrium, the solution to a coupled H-M problem is obtained sequentially by first solving the flow problem and then the geomechanical problem. The new fourth-order axisymmetric ADE scheme is called to solve flow problem, resulting in the pore pressure solution p^{n+1} . Note that the increment of pore pressure due to volumetric strain is evaluated in the geomechanical calculation as a zone value which is then distributed to the grid points. The total stress correction due to this pore pressure change is then calculated and updated into the geomechanical calculation. At the end of this geomechanical step, the displacement solution u^{n+1} is obtained. Several geomechanical steps may be taken to bring the system to equilibrium before the computation progresses to the next time step. This sequential procedure is repeated until the desired simulation time is reached.

It is worth mentioning that the geomechanical calculation in FLAC invokes the equations of motion to derive new velocities and displacements from stresses and forces. Strain rates are then derived from velocities, and new effective stresses from strain rates according to the adopted constitutive law. If the water bulk modulus is given, new increments of pore pressure due to pore volume change will also be evaluated from strain rates. This increment is called the mechanical generation of pore pressure. This cycle constitutes one geomechanical step. At the beginning of a H-M simulation, one fluid time step may put the system considerably out of equilibrium, inducing large unbalanced forces in the model. At this stage, many geomechanical steps will be taken for each fluid step. As the consolidation process continues, the changes in fluid pressure will become small, so that the system will remain in equilibrium (Itasca, 2011b).

In this paper, the accuracy and efficiency of SEA-4-AXI will be compared to FLAC's built-in coupled technique called the basic scheme. The basic scheme uses the explicit flow formulation which requires that the fluid

time step size be smaller than a critical value Δt_{cri} . The value is calculated internally based on a discretization of the medium into zones composed of two overlaid triangular elements, in which the nodal fluid flux q is solved by using the Gauss divergence theorem (Itasca 2011b). The merit of SEA-4-AXI is that it removes this time step restriction, leading the explicit coupling technique to yield an efficient H-M simulation without suffering from numerical instability yet still maintaining high numerical accuracy.

5. Axisymmetric consolidation of a circular footing

SEA-4-AXI is first validated to simulate the H-M response of an axisymmetric consolidation of a circular footing known as McNamee's consolidation (McNamee and Gibson, 1960), which is a common problem in geotechnical engineering. A fully saturated soil layer of height $H = 30$ m and width $W = 40$ m is loaded by a constant uniform pressure of $p_0 = 100$ kPa over a circular area of radius $a = 2$ m. The soil is free to drain at the surface but the other boundaries are impermeable. The FD grid is gradually increasing in size toward the right and bottom boundaries of the model, testing the validity of the non-uniform FD approximation in the new axisymmetric ADE scheme (Fig. 8). The material properties for the model are given in Table 1. The model is run to a consolidation time of $t = 250$ years, which is about 112 times the normalized consolidation time t^* for this problem ($t^* = c_v t / a^2$). The simulation in SEA-4-AXI uses $\Delta t = 20$ d, while that in FLAC's basic flow scheme uses $\Delta t_{\text{cri}} = 5$ d.

Note that the paper adopts the sign convention used in rock mechanics that stress and displacement are positive for compression. Unless stated otherwise, all pore pressures are total (initial hydrostatic plus excess pore pressure) and all stresses are effective. Further, the H-M simulations performed in this paper use constant Biot's coefficient $\alpha = 1$, and the coefficient does not change with the mechanical deformation. This is done to justify the two simplifying assumptions in this paper: the ground is elastic and the compressibility of grains is neglected compared to that of the drained bulk modulus K . The effects of using $\alpha \leq 1$ and of varying deformation on the H-M response of consolidation problems can be seen in the study of tunneling in poroplastic medium done by Bobet (2010).

Fig. 9 shows the contour plots for the H-M responses after the simulation has run for 25 years ($t^* = 11$). As one can see, the comparison of the induced H-M responses, i.e. pore pressure, displacement and stress, between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme is very satisfactory. To observe the long-term H-M behaviors, the pore pressure and settlement histories are monitored at various depths (Fig. 10a) and at various lateral distances from the axis of symmetry (Fig. 10b), respectively. The pore pressure is plotted as normalized pore pressure (p/p_0), while the settlement is plotted as the degree of consolidation, U (%). An excellent match is observed in the solutions between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme and between SEA-4-AXI and the analytical calculation given by McNamee and Gibson (1960). As an accuracy comparison, Table 2 compares the degree of consolidation between the numerical solution and the analytical solution at various normalized consolidation times t^* . As can be seen, the average percentage

error of the SEA-4-AXI solution is 0.17% while its maximum percentage error is less than 0.5%.

Fig. 8. Geometry and non-uniform FD grid of the axisymmetric consolidation beneath a circular footing.

Other excellent agreements are observed in the distribution of pore pressure with depth and of settlement with distance from axisymmetric line. At various consolidation times from $t^* = 0.5$ to $t^* = 11$, the pore pressures with depth from SEA-4-AXI match very well with those from FLAC's basic scheme (Fig. 11). Likewise, the agreement on the settlement profiles at $t^* = 0.1$ and 112 between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme is excellent (Fig. 12). In the settlement profile, the other half of the circular footing model (from 0 m to -40 m) is projected symmetrically as the side being modeled.

Because SEA-4-AXI uses a larger time step size than the basic scheme does, it is very efficient at performing the coupled simulation. The computer runtime for this coupled problem is significantly reduced by 50%, from 120 s in FLAC's basic scheme to only 60 s in SEA-4-AXI.

6. H-M analysis of an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground

The potential application of SEA-4-AXI in geotechnical engineering is now demonstrated by simulating the H-M response of an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground. The advancing tunnel is represented by a two-dimensional (2D) axisymmetric model of an unlined circular excavation of radius $R = 2.5$ m and at a depth of $H = 225$ m through an elastic and saturated medium subjected to total isotropic in situ stress of $\sigma_0 = 4.5$ MPa and initial hydrostatic pore pressure of $p_0 = 2.25$ MPa. Tunnel at this depth has been reported by Graziani and Boldini (2012) when investigating the influence of H-M coupling on deep tunnel response in clays. Note that an axisymmetric model with a circular boundary and isotropic stress is an appropriate approximation for very deep tunnels where the half-space conditions corresponding to the ground surface can be disregarded.

Table 1. Material properties for McNamee's problem.

Hydraulic conductivity, k_H (m/d)	Porosity, ϕ	Shear modulus, G (Pa)	Drained bulk modulus, K (Pa)	Fluid bulk modulus, K_w (Pa)	Constant surface load, p_0 (kPa)	Diffusivity, c_v (m^2/d)	Smallest grid size, $\Delta x \times \Delta y$ (m $\times$ m)	Largest grid size, $\Delta x \times \Delta y$ (m $\times$ m)	Number of zones
1.2×10^{-4}	0.3	2.3×10^5	1.5×10^5	2×10^9	100	0.005	0.5×0.5	4.0×3.5	480

Fig. 9. Contours of (a) pore pressure, (b) radial displacement and (c) effective vertical stress after 25 years of consolidation (comparison between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme).

Fig. 10. Histories of (a) pore pressure and (b) degree of consolidation at various monitoring points.

Table 2. Comparison of the degree of consolidation U (in %) between SEA-4-AXI and the analytical solution at various normalized consolidation times t^* .

t^*	Degree of consolidation, U (%)		Error (%)	Average error (%)
	SEA-4-AXI	Analytical		
0.1	43.01	43.03	0.03	0.17
0.5	72.33	72.23	0.14	
2.8	89.32	89.09	0.26	
5.6	92.97	92.54	0.47	
11.2	95.14	94.97	0.18	
22.5	96.75	96.81	0.06	
45	98.13	98.35	0.22	
100	100.0	100	0	

Fig. 11. Profiles of pore pressure with depth at various consolidation times.

Fig. 12. Profiles of settlement at early ($t^* = 0.1$) and after long-term ($t^* = 112$) consolidation.

The FD grid is also gradually increasing in size toward the right and top boundaries of the model (Fig. 13a). The model boundaries are impermeable except the tunnel wall and face which are made permeable. The advance of the tunnel starts from $x/D = 10$ to the final tunnel face at $x/D = 0$. The advance is simulated by progressively deactivating 40 FD regions of thickness $\Delta x = 1.25$ m ($D/4$) over an excavation period of 10 d, implying the excavation rate of $v_a = 5$ m/d (Fig. 13b).

During deactivation of each region Δx , a practically instantaneous face advance is being simulated for an excavation period of $\Delta t = 0$ (undrained loading), followed by a drained consolidation for a period of $\Delta t = \Delta x/v_a$ (drained loading). This step-by-step excavation, represented by the

alternating stages of undrained excavation and drained consolidation, is performed until the final tunnel face at $x/D = 0$ is reached. The response of the ground surrounding the tunnel shortly after the final tunnel face is reached is called the short-term response. This state also corresponds to the start of the standstill period ($t^* = 0$). This long-term consolidation is performed until the total period of 930 d ($t^* = 100$) is reached. The normalized consolidation time t^* is calculated as $t^* = R^2/c_v$ (Giraud and Rousset, 1996; Li, 1999). The ground properties for this problem are given in Table 3.

The simulation in SEA-4-AXI uses $\Delta t = 20$ min while that in FLAC uses $\Delta t_{\text{cri}} = 5$ min. As expected, SEA-4-AXI reduces the computer runtime by 42%, from 520 s in FLAC's basic scheme to only 300 s in SEA-4-AXI. Discussion in this section will be mainly on the accuracy comparison between the results from SEA-4-AXI and those from FLAC's basic scheme.

Fig. 14a–d shows the contours of pore pressure, radial displacement and stress fields in the short term. The agreement between the contours from SEA-4-AXI and those from FLAC's basic scheme is very satisfactory. Near the tunnel face, the instantaneous pore pressure develops within a short distance of $-0.5D$ toward the advance core (Fig. 14a). For a detailed look at the induced H-M response in the short- and long-term consolidations, the longitudinal profiles of the pore pressure, radial displacement and effective stresses at the tunnel wall are plotted along the axis of the tunnel (Fig. 15). As seen previously, there appears to be a short-term pore pressure buildup up to 2.65 MPa in the region just ahead of the tunnel face (Fig. 15a). In this region, the pore pressure ahead of the core does not have time to dissipate at a speed comparable to the excavation progress due to the nature of ground diffusivity. As drainage proceeds with time, the steep pore pressure gradient decreases, transitioning the pore pressure in the ground towards its steady state as represented by the long-term profile. This non-monotonic behavior and increase of pore pressure above the initial hydrostatic value are analogous to the so-called Mandel-Cryer effect (Mandel, 1953; Cryer, 1963; Abousleiman et al., 1996; Gutierrez and Lewis, 2002). In tunneling, the Mandel-Cryer effect was also observed at the tunnel crown and was caused by the stress concentration in the stiffer zone that is still undrained (Prasetyo and Gutierrez, 2016a, b). Due to the dissipation of pore pressure, the radial displacement also increases with time (Fig. 15b) as well as the effective stresses (Fig. 15c).

It can also be seen from Fig. 15 that the agreement between the H-M responses from SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme is excellent with the average percentage difference well below 2% in both short- and long-term consolidations. As shown in Tables 4–7, the average percentage differences for pore pressure, radial displacement, effective radial stress, and effective tangential stress in the short-term are 0.67%, 0.58%, 1.31%, and 0.41%, respectively, while those in the long-term are 1.79%, 0.78%, 0.92%, and 0.61%, respectively.

To capture the transient H-M response during the excavation period, a monitoring point is placed at $x/D = 5$ (see the top inset in Fig. 16). The excavation starts at $x/D = 10$ (at $t = 0$) and finishes at $x/D = 0$ (at $t = 10$ d). The agreement in the induced H-M responses with time between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme is again very satisfactory (Fig. 16). SEA-4-AXI can capture the excess pore pressure that develops before the tunnel face arrives at the monitoring point at $t = 3$ d (at $x/D = 7$) before it falls sharply as the tunnel face passes the point. Similar behavior is observed for the convergence history in Fig. 16b, while the corresponding effective stresses are shown in Fig. 16c. Note that the jagged shape in the plot of the H-M response is due to the application of the alternating undrained and drained loadings during the tunnel excavation. This wavy response is expected

because the face is advanced at practically instantaneous excavation period $\Delta t = 0$ (the vertical segment) before it is allowed to consolidate for the period of $\Delta t = 0.25$ d (the horizontal segment). The jagged shape has also been reported in the previous coupled analysis of tunneling in shallow ground (Callari and Casini, 2005).

During the standstill period, the convergence and the extrusion at various locations in the ground ahead of the face are also monitored (Fig. 17a and b, respectively). For graphical presentation, extrusion is regarded as positive deformation in this paper. As expected, the convergence and the extrusion located at the face ($0D$) are the largest. The convergence δ_{r0} increases by 20% during the standstill period from 1.2 cm at $t = 10$ d to 1.4 cm at $t = 930$ d, while the face extrusion u_{ex0} increases up to 39%, from 3.3 cm to 4.5 cm. Fig. 17c shows the extrusion across the face height at both standstill periods. The face extrusions from SEA-4-AXI are very satisfactory in matching those from FLAC's basic scheme with the average percentage differences of 0.85% and 0.63% at $t = 10$ d and 930 d, respectively (Table 8). At other locations ahead of the face (at $-1D$ and $-2D$), the convergence, δ_{r1} and δ_{r2} , and the core extrusion, u_{ex1} and u_{ex2} , follow the same trend as those at the face but to a much lesser degree.

7. Conclusions

The main goal of this paper was to eliminate the drawbacks in the standard ADE so that the new ADE scheme can be coupled with a geomechanical simulator for an efficient simulation of axisymmetric coupled problems in non-uniform grid. This goal was achieved by presenting a novel high-order ADE scheme capable of solving the axisymmetric fluid flow problem in a non-uniform grid configuration. The new scheme was derived by performing a fourth-order finite difference approximation of the spatial derivatives of the axisymmetric fluid-diffusion equation under a non-uniform grid configuration. The implicit Crank–Nicolson technique was then applied to the resulting approximation, and the subsequent equation was split into the forward and reverse sweeps, giving rise to the new axisymmetric ADE scheme. The pore pressure solutions from the new scheme were then sequentially coupled with an existing geomechanical simulator in FLAC. This coupling procedure is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order axisymmetric ADE scheme or SEA-4-AXI. By means of von Neumann and truncation error analyses, the new axisymmetric ADE scheme has been proven to be unconditionally stable, consistent

Fig. 13. The Advancing tunnel problem showing (a) geometry and (b) excavation steps.

Table 3. Ground properties for advancing tunnel problem.

Hydraulic conductivity, k_H (m/s)	Porosity, ϕ	Shear modulus, G (Pa)	Drained bulk modulus, K (Pa)	Fluid bulk modulus, K_w (Pa)	Diffusivity, c_v (m^2/s)	Smallest grid size, $\Delta r \times \Delta x$ (m $\times$ m)	Largest grid size, $\Delta r \times \Delta x$ (m $\times$ m)	Number of zones
5×10^{-10}	0.4	1.3×10^8	1.3×10^8	2×10^9	2.6×10^{-4}	0.5×1.25	5×2.5	1560

Fig. 14. Contours of (a) pore pressure, (b) radial displacement, (c) effective radial and (d) tangential stresses after the short-term consolidation (comparison between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme).

Fig. 15. Longitudinal profiles of (a) pore pressure, (b) radial displacement, and (c) effective stresses at the tunnel wall after the short- and long-term consolidation.

Table 4. Comparison of the pore pressure p along the axis of the tunnel between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme.

x/D	p from SEA-4-AXI (MPa)		p from FLAC's basic scheme (MPa)		Difference (%)	
	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term
-10	2.25	2.18	2.25	2.16	0	0.83
-9	2.25	2.17	2.25	2.15	0	0.81
-8	2.25	2.16	2.25	2.14	0	0.81
-6	2.25	2.11	2.26	2.09	0.44	0.93
-5	2.26	2.06	2.26	2.04	0.2	1.02
-4	2.26	1.99	2.26	1.97	0.09	1.14
-3	2.27	1.88	2.27	1.86	0	1.29
-1	2.61	1.36	2.65	1.33	1.51	2.12
0	1.5	0.54	1.5	0.51	0	6.05
1	1.04	0.35	1.07	0.35	3.15	1.87
1.5	0.99	0.33	1.01	0.33	1.37	1.63
2	0.95	0.32	0.96	0.32	0.95	1.52
2.5	0.91	0.31	0.91	0.31	0.26	1.48
3.75	0.82	0.3	0.83	0.3	0.67	1.48
5	0.76	0.29	0.77	0.29	0.86	1.64
6.25	0.71	0.29	0.72	0.29	1.09	1.8
7.5	0.68	0.29	0.69	0.28	0.68	2.12
8.75	0.66	0.29	0.66	0.28	0.64	2.48
10	0.65	0.29	0.65	0.28	0.76	2.9
Average					0.67	1.79

Table 5. Comparison of the radial displacement u_r along the axis of the tunnel between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme.

x/D	u_r from SEA-4-AXI (cm)		u_r from FLAC's basic scheme (cm)		Difference (%)	
	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term
-10	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0	0
-9	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.00	0
-8	0.1	0.24	0.1	0.24	0	0.57
-6	0.1	0.29	0.1	0.28	1.14	2.44
-5	0.11	0.3	0.11	0.3	0.74	0
-4	0.1	0.38	0.1	0.37	0	2.70
-3	0.1	0.46	0.1	0.45	0	2.22
-1	0.28	0.73	0.27	0.71	3.16	2.63
0	1.15	1.37	1.15	1.36	0.48	0.59
1	3.83	4.02	3.9	4.07	1.93	1.25
1.5	4.02	4.2	4.06	4.23	1.06	0.71
2	4.1	4.28	4.13	4.3	0.68	0.49
2.5	4.14	4.33	4.16	4.34	0.42	0.34
3.75	4.19	4.4	4.2	4.41	0.23	0.13
5	4.2	4.45	4.21	4.46	0.27	0.2
6.25	4.2	4.48	4.21	4.49	0.22	0.15
7.5	4.2	4.50	4.21	4.51	0.23	0.17
8.75	4.19	4.51	4.21	4.52	0.25	0.18
10	4.22	4.55	4.23	4.55	0.11	0.04

Table 6. Comparison of the effective radial stress σ'_r along the axis of the tunnel between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme.

x/D	σ'_r from SEA-4-AXI (MPa)		σ'_r from FLAC's basic scheme (MPa)		Difference (%)	
	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term
-10	2.25	2.37	2.25	2.38	0.08	0.57
-9	2.25	2.37	2.25	2.38	0.08	0.64
-8	2.25	2.38	2.25	2.4	0.06	0.7
-6	2.25	2.42	2.25	2.44	0.36	0.87
-5	2.24	2.45	2.26	2.48	0.63	0.9
-4	2.26	2.5	2.26	2.52	0.34	0.77
-3	2.28	2.57	2.28	2.58	0.03	0.25
-1	2.07	3.01	2	2.98	3.39	1.22
0	2.2	2.97	2.27	3.04	3.23	2.32
1	1.3	1.9	1.28	1.9	1.94	0.08
1.5	1.4	1.98	1.36	1.94	3.05	1.91
2	1.46	2.01	1.41	1.97	3.17	1.97
2.5	1.49	2.03	1.46	1.99	2.58	1.89
3.75	1.55	2.03	1.54	2.02	0.65	0.30
5	1.61	2.06	1.59	2.04	1.38	0.99
6.25	1.65	2.07	1.62	2.05	1.68	1.06
7.5	1.67	2.08	1.66	2.07	0.8	0.36
8.75	1.71	2.1	1.69	2.09	1.05	0.57
10	1.75	2.14	1.74	2.14	0.34	0.07
Average					1.31	0.92

Table 7. Comparison of the effective tangential stress σ'_θ along the axis of the tunnel between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme.

x/D	σ'_θ from SEA-4-AXI (MPa)		σ'_θ from FLAC's basic scheme (MPa)		Difference (%)	
	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term	Short-term	Long-term
-10	2.25	2.37	2.25	2.38	0.07	0.61
-9	2.25	2.37	2.25	2.39	0.09	0.67
-8	2.25	2.38	2.25	2.4	0.07	0.72
-6	2.25	2.42	2.25	2.44	0.3	0.89
-5	2.24	2.46	2.26	2.48	0.55	0.95
-4	2.26	2.51	2.26	2.53	0.32	0.94
-3	2.27	2.58	2.28	2.6	0.17	0.73
-1	2.19	3.07	2.2	3.08	0.52	0.02
0	3.89	4.42	3.94	4.39	1.24	0.53
1	4.7	4.98	4.68	4.95	0.52	0.7
1.5	4.83	5.09	4.79	5.04	0.75	1.02
2	4.89	5.13	4.85	5.09	0.73	0.87
2.5	4.92	5.16	4.89	5.12	0.66	0.82
3.75	4.96	5.18	4.95	5.16	0.22	0.28
5	4.99	5.22	4.97	5.19	0.55	0.61
6.25	5.01	5.24	4.98	5.22	0.53	0.55
7.5	5.01	5.26	5	5.24	0.2	0.23
8.75	5.03	5.29	5.01	5.27	0.36	0.39

10	5.11	5.37	5.11	5.36	0	0.04
				Average	0.41	0.61

Fig. 16. Transient H-M response during the excavation period for (a) pore pressure, (b) convergence, and (c) effective stresses.

and fourth-order accurate in space. To demonstrate its application in geotechnical engineering, SEA-4-AXI was used to simulate the H-M interaction of a circular footing and of advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground.

Because it used large flow time steps, SEA-4-AXI has resulted in more computationally efficient H-M simulations than the fully coupled approach using FLAC's basic flow scheme while still maintaining numerical stability and high numerical accuracy. Results from the axisymmetric consolidation of a circular footing and of an advancing tunnel in deep saturated ground showed that SEA-4-AXI reduced computer runtime up to 42%–50% that of FLAC's basic scheme. Yet, the accuracy of the H-M response was well maintained as shown by the average percentage difference of only 0.5%–1.8%. This increased computational efficiency and high-order accuracy, together with its capability in solving axisymmetric H-M

problems in non-uniform domains, suggest that SEA-4-AXI holds great promise for solving larger coupled problems in geotechnical engineering.

Fig. 17. Histories of (a) convergence and (b) extrusion during the excavation and standstill periods with the corresponding (c) face profiles.

Table 8. Comparison of the face extrusion u_{ex0} across the face height between SEA-4-AXI and FLAC's basic scheme.

x/D	u_{ex0} from SEA-4-AXI (cm)		u_{ex0} from FLAC's basic scheme (cm)		Difference (%)	
	10 d	930 d	10 d	930 d	10 d	930 d
2.5	1.29	2.63	1.29	2.63	0.56	0.15
2	2.09	3.4	2.13	3.42	1.96	0.71
1.5	2.62	3.91	2.64	3.9	0.88	0.29
1	2.97	4.24	2.97	4.2	0.09	1.03
0.5	3.18	4.44	3.16	4.4	0.72	0.97
0	3.26	4.53	3.24	4.5	0.89	0.62
-0.5	3.18	4.44	3.16	4.4	0.72	0.97
-1	2.97	4.24	2.97	4.2	0.09	1.03
-1.5	2.62	3.91	2.64	3.9	0.88	0.29
-2	2.09	3.4	2.13	3.42	1.96	0.71
-2.5	1.29	2.63	1.29	2.63	0.56	0.15
Average					0.85	0.63

Conflict of interest

The authors wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure at the Colorado School of Mines for partially funding this research under

Grant No. 69A3551747118 of the Fixing America's Surface Transportation Act (FAST Act) of U.S. DoT FY2016. The authors also wish to recognize support from the Center for Underground Construction and Tunneling at the Colorado School of Mines for providing the FLAC key for the simulations performed in this paper.

Appendix

The grid size-dependent constants for Eqs. (33) and (34) are given in Eqs. (A1)–(A5):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left[12a_i + \frac{12m_i}{r_i} - \frac{12\Delta r}{2r_i} a_i + \frac{M_i}{r_i^2} a_i - \frac{M_i}{r_i^3} m_i - \frac{M_i}{r_i} m_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{3N_i}{r_i^3} a_i + \frac{3N_i}{r_i^4} m_i + \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} m_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{N_i}{r_i} a_i (c_j + d_j) + \frac{A_i}{r_i} a_i - \frac{A_i}{r_i^2} m_i \right. \\ &\quad \left. - A_i m_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{3B_i}{r_i^2} a_i + \frac{3B_i}{r_i^3} m_i + \frac{B_i}{r_i} m_i (c_j + d_j) - B_i a_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{C_j}{r_i} m_i (s_j + t_j) - C_j a_i (s_j + t_j) - \frac{D_j}{r_i} m_i (c_j + d_j) - D_j a_i (c_j + d_j) \right] \\ \alpha_2 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left[12b_i + \frac{12n_i}{r_i} - \frac{12\Delta r}{2r_i} b_i + \frac{M_i}{r_i^2} b_i - \frac{M_i}{r_i^3} n_i - \frac{M_i}{r_i} n_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{3N_i}{r_i^3} b_i + \frac{3N_i}{r_i^4} n_i + \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} n_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{N_i}{r_i} b_i (c_j + d_j) + \frac{A_i}{r_i} b_i - \frac{A_i}{r_i^2} n_i \right. \\ &\quad \left. - A_i n_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{3B_i}{r_i^2} b_i + \frac{3B_i}{r_i^3} n_i + \frac{B_i}{r_i} n_i (c_j + d_j) - B_i b_i (c_j + d_j) - \frac{C_j}{r_i} n_i (s_j + t_j) - C_j b_i (s_j + t_j) - \frac{D_j}{r_i} n_i (c_j + d_j) - D_j b_i (c_j + d_j) \right] \\ \alpha_3 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left[12c_j - \frac{M_i}{r_i} c_j (m_i + n_i) + \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} c_j (m_i + n_i) - \frac{N_i}{r_i} c_j (a_i + b_i) - A_i c_j (m_i + n_i) + \frac{B_i}{r_i} c_j (m_i + n_i) - B_i c_j (a_i + b_i) - C_j s_j (m_i + n_i) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - C_j s_j (a_i + b_i) - D_j c_j (m_i + n_i) - D_j c_j (a_i + b_i) \right] \\ \alpha_4 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left[12d_j - \frac{M_i}{r_i} d_j (m_i + n_i) + \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} d_j (m_i + n_i) - \frac{N_i}{r_i} d_j (a_i + b_i) - A_i d_j (m_i + n_i) + \frac{B_i}{r_i} d_j (m_i + n_i) - B_i d_j (a_i + b_i) - C_j t_j (m_i + n_i) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - C_j t_j (a_i + b_i) - D_j d_j (m_i + n_i) - D_j d_j (a_i + b_i) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (A1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \alpha_5 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} m_i c_j - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} m_i c_j + \frac{N_i}{r_i} a_i c_j + A_i m_i c_j - \frac{B_i}{r_i} m_i c_j + B_i a_i c_j + \frac{C_j}{r_i} s_j m_i + C_j s_j a_i + \frac{D_j}{r_i} c_j m_i + D_j c_j a_i \right) \\ \alpha_6 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} n_i c_j - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} n_i c_j + \frac{N_i}{r_i} b_i c_j + A_i n_i c_j - \frac{B_i}{r_i} n_i c_j + B_i b_i c_j + \frac{C_j}{r_i} s_j n_i + C_j s_j b_i + \frac{D_j}{r_i} c_j n_i + D_j c_j b_i \right) \\ \alpha_7 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} m_i d_j - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} m_i d_j + \frac{N_i}{r_i} a_i d_j + A_i m_i d_j - \frac{B_i}{r_i} m_i d_j + B_i a_i d_j + \frac{C_j}{r_i} t_j m_i + C_j t_j a_i + \frac{D_j}{r_i} d_j m_i + D_j d_j a_i \right) \\ \alpha_8 &= \frac{1}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} n_i d_j - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} n_i d_j + \frac{N_i}{r_i} b_i d_j + A_i n_i d_j - \frac{B_i}{r_i} n_i d_j + B_i b_i d_j + \frac{C_j}{r_i} t_j n_i + C_j t_j b_i + \frac{D_j}{r_i} d_j n_i + D_j d_j b_i \right) \\ \beta_1 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} m_i + \frac{N_i}{r_i} a_i - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} m_i + A_i m_i - \frac{B_i}{r_i} m_i + B_i a_i \right), \quad \beta_2 = \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} (C_j s_j + D_j c_j) \\ \beta_3 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} \left(\frac{M_i}{r_i} n_i + \frac{N_i}{r_i} b_i - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} n_i + A_i n_i - \frac{B_i}{r_i} n_i + B_i b_i \right), \quad \beta_4 = \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} (C_j t_j + D_j d_j) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (A2)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_i &= \frac{2\Delta r_+}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2}, \quad b_i = \frac{2\Delta r_-}{\Delta r_- \Delta r_+^2 + \Delta r_+ \Delta r_-^2}, \quad c_j = \frac{2\Delta z_+}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2}, \quad d_j = \frac{2\Delta z_-}{\Delta z_- \Delta z_+^2 + \Delta z_+ \Delta z_-^2}, \quad m_i = -\frac{1}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-} \\ n_i &= \frac{1}{\Delta r_+ + \Delta r_-}, \quad s_j = -\frac{1}{\Delta z_+ + \Delta z_-}, \quad t_j = \frac{1}{\Delta z_+ + \Delta z_-} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (A3)$$

The constant α_0 is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= \frac{\alpha_N}{\alpha_D} \\ \alpha_N &= 1 - \frac{1}{2} c_v \Delta t \left[a_i + b_i + c_j + d_j + \frac{1}{r_i} (m_i + n_i) - \frac{\Delta r}{2r_i} (a_i + b_i) \right] - \frac{1}{24} c_v \Delta t \left\{ M_i \left[\frac{1}{r_i^2} (a_i + b_i) - \frac{1}{r_i^3} (m_i + n_i) - \frac{1}{r_i} (m_i + n_i) (c_j + d_j) \right] + \right. \\ &\quad \left. N_i \left[-\frac{3}{r_i^3} (a_i + b_i) + \frac{3}{r_i^4} (m_i + n_i) + \frac{1}{r_i^2} (m_i + n_i) (c_j + d_j) - \frac{1}{r_i} (a_i + b_i) (c_j + d_j) \right] + A_i \left[\frac{1}{r_i} (a_i + b_i) - \frac{1}{r_i^2} (m_i + n_i) - (m_i + n_i) (c_j + d_j) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + B_i \left[-\frac{3}{r_i^2} (a_i + b_i) + \frac{3}{r_i^3} (m_i + n_i) + \frac{1}{r_i} (m_i + n_i) (c_j + d_j) - (a_i + b_i) (c_j + d_j) \right] + C_j \left[-\frac{1}{r_i} (s_j + t_j) (m_i + n_i) - (s_j + t_j) (a_i + b_i) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + D_j \left[-\frac{1}{r_i} (m_i + n_i) (c_j + d_j) - (a_i + b_i) (c_j + d_j) \right] \right\} - \frac{1}{12} \left[\frac{M_i}{r_i} (m_i + n_i) + \frac{N_i}{r_i} (a_i + b_i) - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2} (m_i + n_i) + A_i (m_i + n_i) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$+B_i(a_i + b_i) - \frac{B_i}{r_i}(m_i + n_i) + C_j(s_j + t_j) + D_j(c_j + d_j) \Big] \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_D &= 1 + \frac{1}{2}c_v \Delta t \left[a_i + b_i + c_j + d_j + \frac{1}{r_i}(m_i + n_i) - \frac{\Delta r}{2r_i}(a_i + b_i) \right] + \frac{1}{24}c_v \Delta t \left\{ M_i \left[\frac{1}{r_i^2}(a_i + b_i) - \frac{1}{r_i^3}(m_i + n_i) - \frac{1}{r_i}(m_i + n_i)(c_j + d_j) \right] + \right. \\ N_i &\left[-\frac{3}{r_i^3}(a_i + b_i) + \frac{3}{r_i^4}(m_i + n_i) + \frac{1}{r_i^2}(m_i + n_i)(c_j + d_j) - \frac{1}{r_i}(a_i + b_i)(c_j + d_j) \right] + A_i \left[\frac{1}{r_i}(a_i + b_i) - \frac{1}{r_i^2}(m_i + n_i) - (m_i + n_i)(c_j + d_j) \right] \\ &+ B_i \left[-\frac{3}{r_i^2}(a_i + b_i) + \frac{3}{r_i^3}(m_i + n_i) + \frac{1}{r_i}(m_i + n_i)(c_j + d_j) - (a_i + b_i)(c_j + d_j) \right] + C_j \left[-\frac{1}{r_i}(s_j + t_j)(m_i + n_i) - (s_j + t_j)(a_i + b_i) \right] \\ &+ D_j \left[-\frac{1}{r_i}(m_i + n_i)(c_j + d_j) - (a_i + b_i)(c_j + d_j) \right] - \frac{1}{12} \left[\frac{M_i}{r_i}(m_i + n_i) + \frac{N_i}{r_i}(a_i + b_i) - \frac{N_i}{r_i^2}(m_i + n_i) + A_i(m_i + n_i) \right. \\ &\left. + B_i(a_i + b_i) - \frac{B_i}{r_i}(m_i + n_i) + C_j(s_j + t_j) + D_j(c_j + d_j) \right] \quad (\text{A5}) \end{aligned}$$

The grid size-dependent constants for Eqs. (37) and (38) are given in Eq. (A6):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= \frac{\alpha_N}{\alpha_D} \\ \alpha_N &= 1 - \frac{1}{24}c_v \Delta t [12(2b_i + c_j + d_j) - b_i(\Delta r^2 + 2D_j)(c_j + d_j) - 2C_j b_i(s_j + t_j)] - \frac{1}{12}[b_i \Delta r^2 + C_j(s_j + t_j) + D_j(c_j + d_j)] \\ \alpha_D &= 1 + \frac{1}{24}c_v \Delta t [12(2b_i + c_j + d_j) - b_i(\Delta r^2 + 2D_j)(c_j + d_j) - 2C_j b_i(s_j + t_j)] - \frac{1}{12}[b_i \Delta r^2 + C_j(s_j + t_j) + D_j(c_j + d_j)] \\ \alpha_2 &= \frac{b_i}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t [24 - \Delta r^2(c_j + d_j) - 2C_j(s_j + t_j) - 2D_j(c_j + d_j)] \\ \alpha_3 &= \frac{c_j}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(12 - b_i \Delta r^2 - 2b_i C_j \frac{s_j}{c_j} - 2b_i D_j \right) \\ \alpha_4 &= \frac{d_j}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t \left(12 - b_i \Delta r^2 - 2b_i C_j \frac{t_j}{d_j} - 2b_i D_j \right) \\ \alpha_6 &= \frac{b_i}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t (\Delta r^2 c_j + 2C_j s_j + 2D_j c_j) \\ \alpha_8 &= \frac{b_i}{12\alpha_D} c_v \Delta t (\Delta r^2 d_j + 2C_j t_j + 2D_j d_j) \\ \beta_2 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} (C_j s_j + D_j c_j), \quad \beta_3 = \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} (\Delta r^2 b_i) \\ \beta_3 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} (C_j t_j + D_j d_j), \quad \Delta r = r_{i+1,j} - r_{i,j} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{A6})$$

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